

193 **Table S5.** Hysteresis parameters data (used VSM 8604) of Australasian tektites from South China.

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Sample ID	Type	Sampling Location	$M_s (\times 10^{-4} \text{Am}^2/\text{kg})$	$M_{rs} (\times 10^{-6} \text{Am}^2/\text{kg})$	B_c (mT)	B_{cr} (mT)
HN1-2	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	3.99	8.22	5.41	15.49
HN2-2	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	5.29	36.32	10.71	30.75
HN3-2	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	3.53	10.10	8.03	no data
HN4-2	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	4.37	15.49	7.13	21.83
HN5-2	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	3.86	14.81	9.38	30.75
HN6-2	Muong Nong-type	Hainan Province	8.08	136.00	16.21	34.00
HNWC-2	Splash-form	Hainan Province	1.65	9.74	4.29	no data
HNDF-S1	Splash-form	Hainan Province	2.65	7.41	7.42	no data
HNHK-S1	Splash-form	Hainan Province	1.15	17.26	9.44	no data
GDWC-S1	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	1.42	19.16	13.39	no data
GDLZ-S2	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	2.75	7.56	7.80	no data
GDZJ-S4-2	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	3.22	3.30	3.56	no data
GDZJ-S3	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	3.37	5.85	4.53	no data
GDZJ-S5	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	3.30	7.10	7.11	no data
GDZJ-S7	Splash-form	Guangdong Province	7.86	17.67	2.33	no data
GXYL-1	Splash-form	Guangxi Province	2.93	5.90	4.76	no data
GXYL-S2-2	Splash-form	Guangxi Province	2.08	4.13	4.80	no data

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